

EFFECT OF ORGANIZATIONAL NARCISSISM ON EMPLOYEE'S JOB SATISFACTION: MEDIATING ROLE OF ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the relationship of Organizational Narcissism with job satisfaction of employees by keeping the Organizational Citizenship Behavior as a mediating variable. Data was collected through standardized questionnaires from employees of FMCG companies in Lahore. Results depict that Organizational Narcissism is significantly positively related with job satisfaction of employees in the presence of Organizational Citizenship Behavior and is beneficial for organization to get positive outcomes. Literature shows that Organizational Narcissism is a prime catalyst for organizational failure however this study, conversely, indicates that narcissism leads to citizenship behavior of employees who are more satisfied with job. Thus, this research has greatly contributed in Organizational Narcissism literature in the context of Pakistan and is also helpful for decision makers concerning future policy making.

KEYWORDS: Organizational Narcissism, Organizational citizenship Behavior, Job satisfaction, FMCG

1. INTRODUCTION

Narcissism has prevailed largely in the society and has attained the attention of researchers because of its impact on the people and organizations. The American Psychiatric Association (2000) defined narcissism as an unpleasant repeated state of an individual for appearing more valuable than actual and to be in need of appreciation from others. Germain (2018) discusses how narcissism demonstrates itself in leaders and managers in organizations and highlight the human and financial price that such employees manifest on organizations. Research shows Narcissism at organizational level is an important issue and may lead toward corporate failure which can be witnessed in the situations occurred in Long Term Capital Management (LTCM) and Enron (Duchon & Drake, 2009). Main focus of this study is Organizational Narcissism which basically can be elaborated as organization forming a narcissistic identity of employees (Whetten, 2006). Organizational identity is based on standards in society; depict perceived shared values of members in organization (He & Brown, 2013). Organizations having a medium narcissism level helped them in achieving their objectives and goals and in long run they got success but on the other hand, if they display high level of narcissism they can be destroyed (Rousseau & Duchon, 2015b). In case of extreme or high level Narcissism unjustifiable deceptive behavior will diffuse across organization as happened in case of Enron (Amernic & Craig, 2010). Some of the qualities which exist in extremely narcissistic organizations are that they are more likely to spend much on administrative salary, overgenerous workplaces and magnificent perquisites like on resorts for high standard meetings, corporate private jets and costly social occasions (Duchon & Burns, 2008). An organization having extreme narcissism tends to exhibit magnificence, rejects criticism and resources are not distributed optimally in extremely self-admiring firms (Rousseau & Duchon, 2015b).

As discussed above moderate level of organizational narcissism has shown positive result in employees. Similarly, a positive organization culture can create a positive behavior in its employees that can be a cause of increase in their potential and better performance and that is a point of time when organizational citizenship behavior emerges, which consist of activities performed by employees other than their formal roles and duties in an organization (Chien, 2004). Wright and Sablinski (2008) suggested that appropriate risk management, better motivation, suitable affirmation, high system functionality and justice can generate Organizational Citizenship Behavior which is crucial for organizations and plays an influential role.

Organizational citizenship behavior fosters positive organizational culture and one aspect of this is improved job satisfaction of employees (Gardner & Pierce, 2011). Job satisfaction has gained worldwide consideration in academics

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as well as in industry. Job satisfaction is employee's consent from his job which shows that how much he is satisfied from his job experience (Ealias & George, 2012). The health of an organization can be assessed through job satisfaction of employees working in it, their quality of service will show whether they are satisfied with their work or not and if the employees are satisfied then that can be seen through their confidence, loyalty and improved work (Crossman & Abou-Zaki, 2003). Positive employee behavior is influenced by job satisfaction as satisfied employees are sincere with their job and they are more beneficial for organization (Sihombing & Gustam, 2007). Interaction between highly satisfied employees and customers is significant for organization as it brings positive long term outcomes for organizations by displaying kind and soft behavior from employees side which they show in the course of meeting with customers as a result of which emotional state of customer permit the employee to make interpersonal bonds (Gounaris & Boukis, 2013). Crossman and Abou-Zaki (2003) clearly stated that job satisfaction is a standard to check the strength of an organization as the human resource is an asset and organization utilized it for betterment of its health.

This research aims at describing the relationship of Organizational Narcissism with Organizational Citizenship Behavior and job satisfaction of employee in the organizations of Pakistan and it will be helpful for Organizations to boost up the level of organizational Citizenship Behavior of their employee and increase job satisfaction in them. Jobs in organizations are supposed to be very brisk and vibrant. Employees have to work very diligently to accomplish their tasks. Different Organizations offer different types of benefits and HR policies for their employees which are advantageous for nourishing human capital. In this aspect, it becomes necessary for the better environment for employees. By keeping in account these facts, this research study has been developed for identifying the relationship of Organizational Narcissism with job satisfaction of employees which in return, help to increase Organizational Citizenship behavior among employees.

1.1. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

This is a dynamic study on the topic of Organizational Narcissism particularly in context of Pakistan as there is a dearth of research on this topic especially with reference to Pakistan. Previously in context of Pakistan, a study by Sabir et al., (2020) explored narcissism among nurses by examining its impact on organizational cynicism with psychological capital playing a mediating role. This study helps to make headway on the topic of organizational Narcissism in geographical context with different populations. In earlier researches Organizational Narcissism has been slightly discussed but this is a sort of unique research study in which the relationship of Organizational Narcissism with Organizational Citizenship behavior and Job satisfaction of employee has been studied with following research objectives:

- The prime and underlying objective of this research is to check whether there is any kind of relationship among Organizational Narcissism, Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) and Job satisfaction of employees.
- To study about the mediating role of Organizational Citizenship Behavior between Organizational Narcissism and Job Satisfaction.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. ORGANIZATIONAL NARCISSISM

Germain (2018) studied the harmful effects of personality disorders present in corporate leaders, especially in the context of organizational variables such as employee productivity, motivation, satisfaction, retaining etc and concludes that apart from the negative effects, narcissism at workplace also offers solutions and important strategies for employees, human resource specialists and organizational leaders by helping them to enhance business functions and improve employee's job satisfaction and overall wellbeing. Organizations have their own unique culture and defense mechanism which provide security to its employees which are its human assets as well as to its stake holders (Gioia, Patvardhan, Hamilton, & Corley, 2013). Individuals with normal or moderate narcissism have a tendency to show excellent mental condition as research shows healthy narcissism is related to reduction in hopelessness, setting apart from others, anxiousness, mental disturbance and increased personal welfare, betterment of social life and sentimental stability such as the state of equilibrium in negative and positive aspect of life (Giacomin & Jordan, 2016). Grant and McGhee (2013) worked on a case of failed corporate governance and concluded that management control had a significant role in sustaining and preserving the Organizational Narcissism. Shah et al., (2020) studied narcissism's role in promoting unethical organizational behavior examining the role of organizational change as a moderator between unethical and narcissistic behavior. Anand, Ashforth, and Joshi (2004) identified the causes of corruption in organizations and concluded that leaders having narcissistic personality swayed their employees and injected narcissistic proneness in them. Once this execution of narcissism flattered in organization then the employees will prioritize own needs and may precede narcissistic behavior without self-condemnation. Organizational Narcissism consists of four further dimensions named as entitlement and superiority, denial and rationalization, self-aggrandizement and exhibitionism (Tietjen & Myers, 1998). *Entitlement or Superiority* states that organization having

superior identity and demanding an extraordinary treatment. *Denial or Rationalization* states that the organization denies any event which is against its status or identity and imposes those events to others. *Self-aggrandizement* states that the organization having command over others and trying to make its position stronger. *Exhibitionism* describes that Narcissistic organization tries to capture the attention of others and make it possible to impose itself to others (Rousseau & Duchon, 2015a).

2.2. JOB SATISFACTION

Job satisfaction is one of the most researched area in the field of organizational psychology and it is also among the main factors influencing employee's experience at workplace (Imtiaz et al., 2018). Luthans et al., (2007) has defined it as an enjoyable state resulting from the evaluation of one's job experience. Herzberg two factor theory also highlights intrinsic and extrinsic job satisfaction notion. Igalens and Roussel (1999) described factors of employee job satisfaction as *Intrinsic Satisfaction, Extrinsic Satisfaction, Recognition, Authority/Social Unity*. According to Kosteas (2009) job satisfaction is one of the main topics of research in the fields of management, organizational behavior and human resource management.

2.3. ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR

Wen et al. (2016) worked on Organizational citizenship behavior and concluded that the mistreatment from the customer side had a negative effect on Organizational citizenship behavior indicating a negative co-relation observed between these two variables study resulted that employees' internal service behavior intention significantly affects service-oriented organizational citizenship behavior. Literature shows five dimensions of Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Organ, Podsakoff, & MacKenzie, 2005). *Altruism* described as helping others in completing the organizational tasks and problems. *Conscientiousness* can be defined as performing one's tasks more than the minimum requirements. *Sportsmanship* can be stated as staying helpful for others when needed and tolerating others patiently without complaining. *Courtesy* can be described as staying helpful to others and solving their problems. *Civic Virtue* stated as taking a keen interest in the organizational life.

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Following Theoretical Framework has been developed on the support of literature Review.

Figure 1: Relationship between Organizational Narcissism, Organizational Citizenship Behavior & Job Satisfaction of Employee.

Source: Adapted from Rousseau & Duchon (2015b) and Organ, Podsakoff, & MacKenzie (2005) and Igalens & Roussel (1999).

In the above framework Organizational Narcissism is the independent variable, Dependent variable is Employee Job Satisfaction and Organizational Citizenship Behavior is the mediating variable.

3.1. ORGANIZATIONAL NARCISSISM AND ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR

Organizational Narcissism at moderate level is helpful for creating Organizational Citizenship Behavior. Organizational Citizenship Behavior is most important behavior for creating harmony among employees. The cultures, norms, values of organizations are established by employees of an organization. In case if employees are highly narcissistic subsequently, the environment of organization will be shoddy. Healthy Organizational Narcissism formulate significance of Organization for its employees, this worthiness of an organization creates the favorable and supportive mind-set of employees for their co-workers furthermore, develop Organizational Citizenship Behavior. Based on this relationship following first hypothesis can be drawn:

H₁: There is a positive relationship between Organizational Narcissism and Organizational Citizenship Behavior

3.2. ORGANIZATIONAL NARCISSISM & JOB SATISFACTION

Mathieu (2013) has described Narcissism to be significantly positively related to personality, particularly it is highly negatively co-related with agreeableness and has a significant influence on job satisfaction of employees. High narcissism has vital and negative effect on job satisfaction as researched by Mathieu (2013) and results found in his research imply prime facts for management while recruitment of narcissistic individuals rather they are advantageous for organization. Research of Gardner and Pierce (2011) aimed to find out association of Narcissism with job satisfaction, job involvement and motivation to be positive and results showed Narcissistic people tend to perform their duties to satisfy their self-showing needs. Association among Narcissism, leadership and productive behavior at workplace has been checked several times but number of researches which have studied effects of narcissism on work-place behaviors are scarce (Mathieu, 2013). At organizational level, due to the reason of social identity and because of having collective self-esteem the overall effect of Organizational Narcissism on job satisfaction of employee is supposed to be positive (Phipps et al., 2013). Based on above mentioned literature second hypothesis is as follows:

H₂: There is a positive relationship between Organizational Narcissism and job satisfaction of employee

3.3. ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR & JOB SATISFACTION

Research of Munyon, Hochwarter, Perrewé, and Ferris (2010) stated Organizational citizenship behavior is linked positively with highly satisfied employees, having self-confidence rather than which were pessimistic. It was mentioned in research of Foote and Tang (2008) that OCB is highly positively associated with employee's job satisfaction. Zhang and Chen (2013) claimed that Organizational Citizenship Behavior is hypothesized as organizational related behavior representing faithfulness towards organization. Many researchers have worked on the variables of employee's job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior and an adequate amount of literature has been demonstrated on these variables (Foote & Tang, 2008). Employee's job satisfaction rate is high in those organizations where organizational citizenship is frequent (MacKenzie, Podsakoff, & Fetter, 1993). Bowling, Wang, and Li (2012) stated that the attitudes of employees toward their jobs were empirically and conceptually connected with Organizational Citizenship behavior. Theoretically, a straightforward relationship is present between job satisfaction of employee and OCB. Organizational Citizenship Behavior and job satisfaction are closely related and have some similar factors which make these two variables connected. Consequently, it can be concluded that if an employee is showing organizational citizenship behavior then he is mentally satisfied from his job. Therefore, the third hypothesis is:

H₃: There is a direct and positive relationship between Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Job satisfaction of employee.

3.4. ORGANIZATIONAL NARCISSISM, JOB SATISFACTION & ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR

At an individual-level if an employee shows narcissistic behavior with his co-workers then the organization will be affected negatively. The workers will have no co-operation among them but when organization-level narcissism is considered then due to a separate social identity of an organization and combined self-esteem the outcomes on Organizational Citizenship Behavior of employees afterward are positive rather than negative. Organizations having moderate level of narcissism represent common vision through robust diction and rituals this could be efficacious to gain positive consequences. This positive sense of maintaining self-esteem has a strong connection with moderate level of Narcissism hence, it bestows job satisfaction of employee at a collective level by exhibiting organizational citizenship behavior in employees. Thus, the fourth hypothesis is as follows:

H₄: The relationship between Organizational Narcissism and Job Satisfaction is mediated by Organizational Citizenship Behavior

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study has been conducted to be familiarized with the views of Managerial and Non-managerial staff of FMCG (Fast Moving Consumer Goods) organizations currently working in Lahore, Pakistan about Organizational Narcissism, Job Satisfaction and Organizational Citizenship. Moreover, current study has been intended to find out the strength of the relationship of Organizational Narcissism with job satisfaction and Organizational Citizenship Behavior. The nature of this research is descriptive and explanatory. Quantitative research approach has been used for this research. The research sample of this study is based on managerial and non-managerial staff of FMCG Organizations currently working in Lahore. The purpose of choosing this sample was to collect data easily and conveniently from these respondents therefore convenience sampling was used for collecting the responses. The sample is chosen at one point of time so this research is Cross-sectional. A compiled survey instrument including the 5-point Likert scale standardized questionnaires on Independent variable 'Organizational Narcissism' which was

developed by (Rousseau & Duchon, 2015b) and Dependent variables 'Job satisfaction' (Weiss, Dawis, & England, 1967) and Organizational Citizenship Behavior' (Fox & Spector, 2008) has been used for Data Collection.

5. DATA ANALYSIS

In this research analysis has been conducted by using the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) 20.400 questionnaires were given to respondents for measuring their responses regarding this particular research. Out of these 400 questionnaires 27 were not returned, 39 were not completely filled. Fortunately, 334 usable questionnaires were returned with no missing values. Response rate which is also called return rate was 83.5%.

5.1. FACTOR ANALYSIS

All questionnaires were standardized but for making questions valid according to Pakistani firms' culture factor analysis was conducted. Questions having suppressed values less than 0.4 were deducted from independent, mediator and dependent variable. Total number of remaining questions after conducting factor analysis was 56, out of which Organizational Narcissism have 23 questions, 13 questions were of OCB, Job satisfaction have 16 questions and 4 questions were related to demographic variables.

5.2. INTERPRETATION OF KMO AND BARTLETT'S TEST

In case of this particular research, the value of KMO is 0.825 for Organizational Narcissism, 0.855 for Organizational Citizenship behavior and 0.861 for Job satisfaction which are in between 0.8 and 1 so, the sample of research is adequate. In this research, Bartlett's Test of Sphericity value showed that 95% level of significance and $\alpha = 0.05$ which exhibit p-value (Sig.) of $.000 < 0.05$ consequently, factor analysis is viable.

Table 1: KMO and Bartlett's Test

	KMO	Bartlett's Test Df	Sig
Organizational Narcissism	0.825	351	0.000
Organizational Citizenship behavior	0.855	190	0.000
Job satisfaction	0.861	190	0.000

5.3. RELIABILITY

In this research, the value of Cronbach's Alpha for Organizational Narcissism is 0.855 which consisted of 23 items, Organizational Citizenship behavior has 0.870 Cronbach's Alpha for 13 items moreover, for Job satisfaction, value of reliability coefficient is 0.892 for 16 items. All the values of Cronbach's Alpha for respective variables are greater than 0.70 which are highly acceptable (Peters, 2014).

5.4. DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS

Descriptive Analysis was undertaken to measure Means and standard deviations of each variable respectively. Organizational Narcissism has mean value of 3.4850, Organizational Citizenship behavior has 3.6640 and Job satisfaction has 3.6632. Here, Organizational Narcissism has 0.45048, Organizational Citizenship behavior has 0.47977 and Job satisfaction has 0.47981 Standard Deviation values respectively.

5.5. PEARSON'S CORRELATION ANALYSIS

Pearson's correlation values for ON, OCB and JS (N=334) result showed that ON and OCB have strong positive relationship ($r=0.601$, $N=334$, $p=0.01$, two-tailed), another strong positive correlation existed between JS and ON ($r=.572$, $N=334$, $p=0.01$, two-tailed). Moreover, OCB and JS have strong positive relationship ($r=.615$, $N=334$, $p=0.01$, two-tailed). Required Pearson's correlation analysis of ON, OCB and JS (N=334) was fulfilled so, regression can be conducted on this research data.

5.6. REGRESSION ANALYSIS

In the first hypothesis the relationship of Organizational Narcissism has been shown with Organizational Citizenship Behavior. The value of R-square was calculated as 0.361 which showed that there is a positive relationship between Organizational Narcissism and Organizational citizenship behavior. Here in this hypothesis the value of Adjusted R-square is 0.359 which showed that 35.9% variation in Organizational citizenship behavior is due to Organizational Narcissism. F-value tells about the degree of freedom of model which is $F(1,332) 187.690$ $p < 0.05$ and t-value is 13.700 which depicts that the null hypothesis has been rejected and Alternative hypothesis (H_1) which is 'There is a direct and positive relationship between Organizational Narcissism and Organizational Citizenship Behavior' has accepted furthermore, the model is statistically significant. As shown in table 2, B value is 0.640 which tells about the direction of the relationship which is positive between Organizational narcissism and organizational citizenship behavior and further explains that 1 unit change in Organizational narcissism causes change in organizational citizenship behavior.

Table 2: Regression Analysis of H1

	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	T	Sig	Unstandardized Beta
H1	0.601	0.361	0.359	187.690	13.700	0.000	0.640

Second hypothesis consisted of Organizational narcissism as independent variable and job satisfaction of employees as dependent variable. Value of R-square is 0.327 and represents a positive relationship between these two variables and can be seen through table.3. Adjusted R-square value is 0.325 which exhibit that a change in level of job satisfaction is due to Organizational narcissism. Degree of freedom value of this hypothesis is F (1,332) 161.468 p<0.05 and t value is 12.707 so, null-hypothesis has rejected and alternative hypothesis has accepted which states that *'There is a direct and positive relationship between Organizational Narcissism and job satisfaction of employee'*. Hence, hypothesis 2 has proved to be statistically significant. B-value is 0.609 which tells that relationship between Organizational Narcissism and job satisfaction of employee is positive.

Table 3: Regression Analysis of H2

	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	T	Sig	Unstandardized Beta
H2	0.572	0.327	0.325	161.468	12.707	0.000	0.609

To check the relationship between Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Job satisfaction in hypothesis 3, Organizational Citizenship Behavior was taken as independent variable and Job satisfaction as dependent variable. Value of R is 0.615 showed in table 4 is a perfect relationship between variables. R-square value is 0.537. Adjusted R-square consisted on the value 0.436. It tells that 83.6% change in Job satisfaction is due to Organizational Citizenship Behavior. F value is F (1,332) 165.926, p<0.05 and t value is 12.220 which explained that hypothesis.3 which is *'There is a direct and positive relationship between Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Job satisfaction of employee'* is accepted and t value has shown in Table.4. B value for this hypothesis is 0.685 and showed that relationship is positive between Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Job satisfaction of employee.

Table 4: Regression Analysis of H3

	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	T	Sig	Unstandardized Beta
H3	0.615	0.537	0.436	165.926	12.220	0.000	0.685

In hypothesis 4 the mediating relationship between Independent, Mediating and Dependent variable has been mentioned. Organizational Narcissism was taken as Independent variable, Organizational Citizenship Behavior is Mediating variable and dependent variable is job satisfaction. Relationship among these variables is strongly positive as value of R-square is 0.624 and Adjusted R-square value is 0.511 as shown in table 5 explaining that Organizational Narcissism in the presence of Organizational Citizenship behavior causes the 51.1% variation in Job satisfaction of employees. F value is F (1, 332) 174.651, p<0.05 and t value is 11.832 which describe that the hypothesis 4, *"the relationship between Organizational Narcissism and job satisfaction is mediated by Organizational Citizenship Behavior"* is partial as direct relationship between organizational narcissism and job satisfaction is still significant even after OCB has mediated between them.

Table 5: Regression Analysis of H4

	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	T	Sig	Unstandardized Beta
H4	0.723	0.624	0.511	174.651	11.832	0.000	0.714

6. DISCUSSION

This study was aimed to find out the relationship between Organizational Narcissism, Organizational Citizenship behavior and job satisfaction of employees. Different hypotheses were generated to gain knowledge about relationship of Organizational Narcissism with Organizational Citizenship behavior and job satisfaction of employee. Various analyses were conducted by using SPSS and the significance values which were obtained in respective hypotheses showed that relationship among these variables is positive and there is need of further study on these variables at broader level. All of the hypotheses were accepted which showed that Organizational Narcissism can create Organizational Citizenship behavior which further create satisfaction from job in employees. These positive relationships can change the general perception about narcissism and may help the narcissism to come outside from the confines of dark side (Hodson, Hogg, & MacInnis, 2009). Results of this study emphasize that narcissism can be

productive as was suggested by (Maccoby, 2003). This opens up the gate for a broader discussion that how Narcissism can work as a positive variable for Organizational context. The significant results of this research showed that moderate or normal narcissism cause healthy self-esteem and good behavior and is beneficial for people.

7. CONCLUSION

From all the results, analysis and discussion, it can be interpreted that Organizational Narcissism creates Organizational Citizenship Behavior in employees and they perform extra role activities and become more supportive towards each other which proves beneficial for the organization. Further, these activities influence job satisfaction of employees in a positive way and make them engage in their job so they work more diligently. In long-run, improving the job satisfaction of employees results in prosperity and progress of organization as the association between Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Job satisfaction is reciprocal in nature as supported in another research. This research on Organizational Narcissism supports the results of another study which explained the association of Organizational Narcissism with different outcomes.

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